

D4.2 Design of the hot and cold PCM materials and their vessels

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Summary			
<p>This deliverable presents the work undertaken in WP4, Task 4.2: Phase Change Material (PCM) storage material characterisation and optimal implementation in PCM storage vessels. The main objective of this deliverable is to choose the most suitable hot and cold Phase Change Materials (PCMs), report on their properties and interactions with surrounding materials and describe the current status and development of the containing vessels and heat exchangers. Criteria such as material properties, cycle performance and material compatibility are examined. The goal is to develop the most suitable PCMs for implementation in the cold and hot thermal storage units that will be incorporated in the novel, compact, integrated thermal storage system for residential buildings proposed by MiniStor. In addition, the optimal implementation of these PCM materials in corresponding PCM vessels is analysed.</p>			
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
EU	European Union
n.a.	not available
PCM	Phase change material
SAT	Sodium acetate trihydrate
STARe	Thermal analysis software from Mettler Toledo
TBAB	Tetrabutylammonium bromide
tbd	to be decided
T _c	Crystallisation temperature
T _m	Melting temperature
wt%	percent by weight

1 Introduction

Minimal Size Thermal and Electrical Energy Storage System for In-Situ Residential Installation (MiniStor) offers a sustainable solution to harness the energy efficiency potential of the European building stock. During the development of the project, the MiniStor system will be demonstrated and validated at five demonstration sites located in Ireland, Spain, Greece, and Hungary to test its effectiveness in different local climatic conditions, facilitating market replication while offering an innovative, efficient and clean thermal and electrical energy storage solution for all Europeans.

This report presents the work undertaken in WP4, Task 4.2: PCM storage material characterisation and optimal implementation in PCM storage vessels. The main objective of this deliverable is to select optimum hot and cold Phase Change Materials (PCMs), report on their properties and interactions with surrounding materials and describe the current status and development of the containing vessels and heat exchangers. The goal is to develop the most suitable PCMs for implementation in the cold and hot thermal storage units that will be incorporated in the novel, compact, integrated thermal storage system for residential buildings proposed by MiniStor. In addition, the optimal implementation of these PCM materials in corresponding PCM vessels is analysed.

One of the project partners (Sunamp) has already worked extensively on the development and testing of a PCM for high-performance applications in domestic heating and hot water systems; therefore, this prior research can be used as a base for the MiniStor project. One of the hot PCMs researched, which Sunamp has been selling commercially since 2015, meets all the requirements of the MiniStor system. For this reason, this task can focus its efforts on researching cold PCMs.

In this deliverable, different cold PCMs that are already on the market are analysed in more detail to determine their suitability for the project. After initial data review and literature research, a total of 11 materials will be explored further and after a second selection, 5 cold PCMs will be subjected to various tests. In particular, criteria such as:

- Material properties: phase change temperature, subcooling (or supercooling), phase change enthalpy, specific heat capacity and density);
- Cycle performance;
- Material compatibility (aluminium, copper and selected polymers);

are examined. After these tests, the assessment of availability and the calculation of costs, the suitability of all five materials is determined and a recommendation is made for the choice of the optimal PCM for the cold thermal storage unit.

1.1 Phase change material (PCM)

1.1.1 Research

In a latent heat storage system, a phase change material (PCM) undergoes a transformation from solid to liquid and vice versa, to store and release heat. Phase change materials (PCMs) are an ideal medium for thermal energy storage [1]–[5] because of their high energy density and isothermal charging and discharging profiles. In a typical working temperature range, the storage capacity of latent heat storage can be 2 to 5 times larger than that of a sensible storage [6]. This leads to a significant decrease in the storage space requirement and makes latent heat storage an attractive storage technology for the use of renewable energy sources, particularly in buildings, where generally space is limited [3].

A rough classification of PCMs can be made in terms of organic and inorganic substances [2]. The most widely considered inorganic PCMs are salt hydrates, which are generally characterised by low purchase prices and high volumetric energy densities but face the issues of corrosiveness to some metals, phase segregation, considerable supercooling effects [7]. The latter two can be bypassed by utilisation of suitable gelling agents and nucleating agents respectively [8]. The most commonly used organic PCMs are paraffin waxes, which are characterized by high flammability and higher prices in a relatively limited melting point range. However, they present high cyclability, low corrosiveness and low supercooling [2], [9]. Esters and sugar alcohols are also the subject of an increasing amount of investigation; the former due to their low supercooling and good cycling stability and the latter due to their high enthalpies of fusion at medium temperature ranges (75°C – 150°C) [2], [9]. Both sugar alcohols and esters can be nature-based which makes them potentially more sustainable than other PCM solutions. Figure 1 presents a summary of the phase change enthalpy of various PCM classes as a function of their melting temperatures.

Figure 1. Overview of melting enthalpies and melting temperatures for different classes of phase change materials (PCMs). Figure taken from [10].

When selecting a PCM for a specific application, several criteria are considered: the PCM needs to exhibit a high phase change enthalpy (generally > 150 J/g), low tendency to supercool, a narrow phase change transition temperature range at the temperature level of interest, fast apparent crystallisation rate, long-term stability over consecutive heating/cooling cycles. Additionally, the PCM should be non-corrosive to its encapsulation medium and non-toxic to humans and the environment.

Table 1 A detailed description of desired PCM properties

Thermal Properties	Physical Properties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase change temperature in the desired operation range A high phase change enthalpy per unit volume A high specific heat capacity to provide significant additional sensible heat High thermal conductivity of both phases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A small volume change on phase transformation A low vapour pressure at the operating temperature Congruent melting and solidification process A high density
Kinetic properties	Chemical properties
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low subcooling effect A high nucleation rate An adequate rate of crystallization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long-term stability Cycle-stability Compatibility with the construction materials Non-toxic, non-flammable and non-explosive to ensure safety

1.1.2 Application

The use of a latent heat storage system using phase change materials (PCMs) is an effective way of storing thermal energy and has the advantages of high-energy storage density and the isothermal nature of the storage process. PCMs have been widely used in latent heat thermal-storage systems for passive room conditioning, heat pumps, solar engineering, and spacecraft thermal control applications.

Based on phase change state, PCMs fall into three groups: solid-solid PCMs, solid-liquid PCMs and liquid-gas PCMs. Among them the solid-liquid PCMs are most suitable for thermal energy storage. The solid-liquid PCMs comprise organic PCMs, inorganic PCMs and eutectics. There are large numbers of PCMs that melt and solidify at a wide range of temperatures, making them attractive in a number of applications.

PCM wallboard is considered to be an effective and less costly replacement of standard thermal mass to store solar heat in buildings, in which the PCM is embedded into a gypsum board, plaster or other building structures. Using PCM wallboard could maintain room temperature within the human comfort zone for long periods of time after the heating or cooling system is shut off.

Another method of applying PCMs into building structures consist of incorporating PCMs into a concrete matrix or open cell cements. This composite is called thermocrete. However, concrete strength might be significantly reduced by incorporation of PCMs.

Heat Batteries are active thermal energy stores based on encapsulated PCM whose stored thermal energy is actively used by transferring it to a fluid e.g. water, water/glycol mixture, oil, or air. The fluid can flow around the micro- or macro-encapsulation to be warmed up, cooled down, or can flow into a heat exchanger immersed in the PCM. Unlike a PCM wallboard, the heat transfer rate in Heat Batteries can be

regulated by controlling the temperature and/or the flow rate of the heat transfer fluid as well as by the design of the heat exchanger and/or of the encapsulation. The biggest advantage of PCM Heat Batteries is that they can store the same amount of energy as a water tank in several-fold less occupied volume. This makes them very practical to install even where space is limited or at premium.

Sunamp Heat Batteries contain inorganic, non-toxic, salt-based phase change materials, which absorb and release thermal energy during the process of melting and freezing. They are designed in standard sizes ranging from 3.5 to 14 kWh/unit (equivalent to 70-210 litres of hot water storage) for the residential market and up to 100 kWh/unit for the commercial and industrial market. They are scalable and modular, and depending on how much energy is needed in a house, office or farm, the number of Heat Batteries can increase. Thanks to a very powerful finned-tube heat exchanger, a Heat Battery can be charged or discharged very quickly. For hot water applications, this allows a traditional water tank to be completely substituted by a Heat Battery with significant space savings. Peak power of 50 kW and sustained power output of >35 kW during the phase change are achieved for the residential products throughout the range. This results in a power density range of 230-581 kW/m³, depending on the size of the storage.

An additional benefit compared to traditional water-based stores is that there is minimal water stored in the Heat Batteries, so there is reduced risk of dangerous over pressurisation events, and a strongly reduced risk of legionella (a bacteria that likes to grow in some hot water tanks if they aren't regularly heated to very high temperatures).

Among other applications, Heat Batteries can be used for: chilled food transport; medicine & vaccine transport; water heating; waste heat storage; heat pumps; air conditioning; frozen food transportation; automotive HVAC applications; temperature-controlled transport.

In MiniStor, Sunamp Heat Batteries will be integrated used for space heating and cooling, and to provide hot water. This system is expected to provide significant savings in CO₂ emissions and fuel bills related to heating and cooling, and it will be developed to be replicated in other retrofitting projects or new constructions.

2 Hot PCM

Sunamp has developed and optimized a variety of high-performance PCMs for heating and hot water applications. These developments were based on exhaustive research to identify the best PCM candidates and substantial testing and optimization of the chosen materials before the final product was presented to the market. Therefore, before searching the literature to identify promising PCM candidates for the hot storage to be integrated in the MiniStor system, the Sunamp PCM catalogue was examined and two previously optimized PCMs were identified that fit the requirements of the MiniStor system.

2.1 SU58

SU58 is a PCM developed by Sunamp Ltd. to serve primarily as a more compact alternative to hot water cylinders for domestic hot water applications. It is based on sodium acetate trihydrate (SAT), which has a high energy density of up to 143 W-hrs/litre (over 10-75 °C), a melting point of 58 °C, is non-corrosive to aluminium and copper, is non-toxic and is not flammable. As with many other salt hydrates, SAT suffers from two significant disadvantages: (i) incongruent melting resulting in phase separation and (ii) a high degree of supercooling. Both of these issues were solved by Sunamp via utilization of appropriate polymers as thickening agents and nucleators to minimize supercooling [8]. The passive operation of the nucleators within the SU58 results in subcooling of <5 °C. This unique formulation has demonstrated stable operation over tens of thousands of cycles and Sunamp was the first heat battery manufacturer in the world to be awarded A grade RAL certification, which is an independent quality mark and the only global standard for PCMs and PCM products. Therefore, SU58 is considered an excellent PCM for the hot storage of the MiniStor project. Table 2 presents some important thermophysical properties of SU58. Table 2. Thermophysical properties SU58 (measured by Sunamp Ltd).

Table 2. Thermophysical properties SU58 (measured by Sunamp Ltd).

Thermophysical property	Abbreviation	Value
Phase change temperature	T_{PC}	58 °C
Specific heat of fusion	h_{PC}	210 ± 5 J/g
Density (liquid)	ρ_l	1180 kg/m ³
Density (solid)	ρ_s	1280 kg/m ³
Specific heat capacity (liquid)	$c_{p,l}$	3.5 J/(g K)
Specific heat capacity (solid)	$c_{p,s}$	2.8 J/(g K)
Heat conductivity (liquid)	λ_l	0.4 W/(m K)
Heat conductivity (solid)	λ_s	0.65 W/(m K)

SU58 has not only demonstrated high performance as a stand-alone PCM but also when integrated in latent heat storage units. Figure 2 shows the power profile of SU58 during solidification. A finned tube heat exchanger was immersed in 17 litres of PCM and encased in a plastic air-tight container, which was thermally insulated. The experiments were conducted with water as the heat transfer fluid. The mass flow rate was kept at 0.1 kg/s for all experiments and the inlet temperature was varied between 15 and 50 °C. As expected, the solidification time increased with increasing water inlet temperature (from 10 min to 45 minutes). In all cases, a clear power plateau could be retained throughout almost the entire solidification process, which clearly demonstrates the excellent performance of the Sunamp Heat Battery. Over 40,000 cycles have been performed on Sunamp Heat Batteries containing SU58, confirming that the Sunamp SAT formulation remains stable in contact with the heat exchanger and the encasing vessel.

Figure 2. Power vs. time during solidification process of SU58 inside a Sunamp heat battery

2.2 SU48

At the start of the MiniStor project the maximum temperature that could be achieved from the TCM decombination reaction or the heat pump was uncertain. Sunamp's SU58 PCM requires an inlet flow temperature $\geq 63^\circ\text{C}$ to melt the PCM, which is not commonly attainable by commercial low temperature heat pumps. In case this temperature was not achievable, Sunamp proposed as an alternative its SU48 PCM, which like the SU58 PCM, is also based on sodium acetate trihydrate. This PCM has the advantage of having similar thermophysical properties to SU58 with only a 5% reduction in latent heat, but with a melting point of 48°C , which is comfortably within the range attainable by commercial low temperature heat pumps. The SU48 formulation is based upon that of SU58 but has additional chemical components that have a melting point depression effect, thus tuning the phase change temperature to one that is still able to be exceeded by off-the-shelf single stage heat pumps/low temperature heat pumps.

Figure 3. A 17L test cell with an early variant of SU48 PCM charged via a recirculation loop at 8 L/min with a 3 kW electrical element, and discharged with 15 °C water at 5 L/min.

In the test shown in Figure 4, the end of charging was at ~63 °C inlet and ~58 °C outlet temperatures (55 °C at the outlet of the test cell could have been selected as end of test as this appears to be no longer in the phase change zone, but rather the liquid zone). Crucially for efficient heat pump operation, the duration for the flow temperature >60 °C to achieve this is minimal. A comparative SU58 test cell would have required a minimum of 60 °C at the outlet (65 °C inlet) during charging to ensure full melting of the PCM; the differences in thermal tolerances are due to the SU48 not having as 'flat' a melting plateau as SU58; i.e. it melts over a broader temperature range.

Upon discharge with 15 °C water at 5 L/min the material cools quickly until it reaches ~42 °C where it nucleates and rapidly (for a PCM during a discharge) increases in temperature reaching a peak of 44.8 °C. This equates to approximately 1.4 kW·hrs of heat delivered above 40 °C, a temperature below which begins to be too cold for DHW usage, and 1.8 kW·hrs to depletion (20 °C outlet temperature).

2.2.1 Key challenges overcome in the development of SU48

There are multiple challenges in the development of a PCM for use in a Heat Battery. There is the PCM formulation itself, of course, but there are many other factors that together determine successful incorporation into a product. Key challenges that were overcome are described below:

Formulation development

Many different potential melting point depression agents were tested, and, for promising candidates, the ideal composition was determined.

Validation of cycle stability at multiple scales

The cycle stability and performance of the PCM was tested at two different scales. Over 8,000 cycles have so far been completed in a 17 litre test cell and over 3,000 cycles in a UniQ Heat Battery. No discommensurable variance in performance has been seen, in terms of energy output or melting and crystallisation temperatures.

Materials compatibility analysis

SU48 has been tested with all Heat Battery components, both plastic and metal. Some discoloration of the PCM arising from leakage of pigment from a polypropylene plastic into the material is being investigated. This is unusual for a salt hydrate PCM, but performance tests show no change, hence this is a purely cosmetic effect that requires further investigation.

Supply chain hurdles

Bulk sources of salts can contain halide impurities. Sunamp heat exchangers contain aluminium components, which are corroded by halide impurities, especially chlorides. Therefore low chloride impurity sources of individual PCM components are crucial. This has been achieved, but there is still a limited supply chain so far.

Process equipment selection and validation

The manufacturing process has been demonstrated first in a 30 litre batch, and then in a 300 litre batch using a redundant manufacturing line for SU58. Process improvement equipment has been identified to turn an 8 hour process into a 1 hour process. The SU58 production line cannot be used as there is a concern of residual matter from the SU48 additives contaminating the SU58 production line. Any effect on the quality of SU58 is unknown and is a source of unwanted variation.

IP protection strategies

A patent has been filed.

Customers engaged for commercial exploitation

Test units have been shipped with evaluation agreements stating the units must be returned after a set time period (for destructive analysis) and on the condition that all test data be shared with Sunamp. This will allow us to analyse the performance of the Heat Battery in the field.

2.2.2 Application in MiniStor

A heat pump capable of achieving ≥ 63 °C was identified for the project, resulting in the decision to select the SU58 PCM. The main advantage is that more energy can be stored in an SU58 Heat Battery and a high outlet temperature is delivered. The SU48 PCM remains available if for any operational or technical reason the chosen heat pump (or the thermochemical recombination process) does not function as expected.

3 Cold PCM

This chapter describes the criteria used to select the cold PCM and the performance of the most important candidates. For this purpose, measurements were carried out with the respective PCMs and the following properties were determined:

- Material properties (phase change temperature, subcooling (or supercooling), phase change enthalpy, specific heat capacity and density)
- Cycle performance over 200 cycles
- Material compatibility (aluminium, copper and selected polymers)

Based on the measurement results, all candidates were evaluated and a suitable PCM was selected.

3.1 Selection

To operate a latent storage system efficiently, a suitable PCM is first required that has a melting and crystallization temperature as close as possible to the process temperature. The identification, analysis, evaluation, and selection of new PCM candidates in the required temperature range was the main task of HSLU in this project.

For the selection of the right PCM several factors were considered, including material performance and material compatibility, as well as economic indicators and availability. An overview of the above criteria is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Overview of all selection criteria

As a first step, a literature research was performed and 11 promising PCM candidates were selected and are shown in Table 3 (S-A = Sigma-Aldrich, Rub. = Rubitherm).

Table 3 Compilation of all PCM candidates from the literature search. For mixed substances, purity refers to the undiluted product from the manufacturer.

Substance (conc. in %)	T _{melt} lit.	Formula	Producer	CAS-No°	Purity	Source
Lithium chlorate trihydrate (63/27)	8.1 °C	$LiClO_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	n.a.	13453-71-9	n.a.	[11]
Potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate (57/43)	9 °C	$KF \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.569) / $KF \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.431)	S-A	7789-23-3	99 %	[12]
Rubitherm SP5 gel	5 °C	n.a.	Rub.	n.a.	n.a.	data sheet
Formic acid	8.4 °C	CH_2O_2	S-A	64-18-6		[11]
n-Tetradecane	6 °C	$C_{14}H_{30}$	S-A	629-59-4	99 %	[11]
Parafol 14-97	5.5 °C	$C_{14}H_{30}$	Parafol	629-59-4	n.a.	data sheet
Rubitherm RT5	5.5 °C	$C_{14}H_{30}$	Rub.	629-59-4	n.a.	data sheet
Tetrahydrofuran / water (20/80)	5 °C	C_4H_8O	S-A	109-99-9	99 %	[13]
TBAB / water (32/68)	9.8 °C	$(CH_3CH_2CH_2CH_2)_4N(Br)$	S-A	1643-19-2	n.a.	[14]
Sunamp SU11	11 °C	$CH_3OCO(CH_2)_4COCH_3$	Sunamp	627-93-0	n.a.	data sheet
Sunamp SU5	5.5 °C	$C_{13}H_{26}O_2$	Sunamp	111-82-0	n.a.	data sheet

3.1.1 Process

Table 4 summarizes all evaluation criteria with the associated weighting factor. Certain criteria must be met, as can be seen in the Mandatory Criteria column. The weight factors are from experience from previous projects.

Table 4 Weighting of the individual evaluation criteria. The weighting factor ranges from 5 (very important) to 0 (no weighting).

	Criteria	Weight factor	Relative weight	Mandatory criteria	Unit
Material performance	Cycle stability (segregation.)	5	16%	No segregation	
	Subcooling	3	9%	none	
	E-density (melting)	5	16%	none	kJ/kg
Material compatibility¹	Hazardousness	3		Not flammable, corrosive or toxic	
	Butyl rubber	2	6%	none	
	Polypropylene	0	0%	none	
	Polyethylene	3	9%	none	
	Al & Cu	3	9%	Al < 74 or Cu < 1500	[mg/ (m ² d)]
	Cu	1	3%	< 1500	[mg/ (m ² d)]
	Al	1	3%	< 74	[mg/ (m ² d)]
Economic indicators and availability	Ease & availability	2	6%	not available	
	PCM cost / kWh	4	13%	none	

From the 11 initial candidates, six PCMs were not pursued further due to their inability to meet one or more mandatory criteria based on literature data. These are listed in Table 5. In the case of the chemically identical PCMs Parafol 14-97, Rubitherm RT5 and n-tetradecane, n-tetradecane was selected. This could be ordered from the supplier Sigma Aldrich with high purity for reproducible results. The purity of Rubitherm and Parafol's own products are not specified.

¹ A maximum corrosion rate in mg per m² and day is defined for the material compatibility of the metals. At this corrosion rate, the heat exchanger will have decomposed after 20 years. More detailed information can be found in the chapter "material compatibility".

Table 5 Excluded candidates for measurement

Substance	Reasons for exclusion
Lithium chlorate trihydrate	Not producible
Formic acid	Hazards such as flammability, toxicity, and corrosivity
Tetrahydrofuran / water	Hazards such as flammability, harmfulness, and health hazard
Potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate (57/43)	Toxicity
Parafol 14-97	Chemically identical to tetradecane
Rubitherm RT5	Chemically identical to tetradecane

3.2 Measurements

The five PCMs that passed the pre-selection round were analysed and evaluated using a detailed test procedure. Some measurements were also conducted with potassium fluoride tetra-/ dihydrate and are presented in this section even though it was rejected from the final list of candidates.

3.2.1 Material properties

Thermophysical properties were determined, the compatibility of the PCMs with relevant metals and polymers was investigated, and the long-term stability was estimated. To determine material performance, properties such as density, enthalpy, melting point, and subcooling were measured.

3.2.1.1 Materials and methods

Table 6 shows the information on the raw materials used as the basis for PCM in this study. Four of the six materials were used directly for analysis without preparation and purification. The salt hydrate potassium fluoride tetra-/ dihydrate had to be prepared. The organic PCM TBAB was mixed with the appropriate amount of deionized water to achieve the final concentration of 32 wt%.

Table 6 Investigated phase change materials

Substance (conc. in %)	Formula	Manufacturer	CAS-No°	Purity
Rubitherm SP5 gel	n.a.	Rubitherm	n.a.	n.a.
n-Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	Sigma-Aldrich	629-59-4	99 %
TBAB / water (32/68)	C ₁₆ H ₃₆ BrN	Sigma-Aldrich	1643-19-2	n.a.
Sunamp SU11	CH ₃ OCO(CH ₂) ₄ COOCH ₃	Sunamp	627-93-0	n.a.
Sunamp SU5	C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₂	Sunamp	111-82-0	n.a.

Determination of phase change temperature and phase change enthalpy

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed using a Mettler Toledo DSC 3+ device with auto-sampler to determine the phase change temperatures and the phase change enthalpies of the five PCM candidates. The device was calibrated and checked prior to the measurements using indium and zinc, following the specifications provided by the device manufacturer.

Figure 5 Example of DSC melting curves from measurements with a heating rate of (top) 10 K/min to determine the phase change enthalpy and (bottom) 2 K/min to determine phase change temperature. In both cases all three repetitions are plotted in the same graph showing the very consistent melting behaviour that n-tetradecane presented.

Heating rates (β) of 10 K/min and 2 K/min were chosen for the determination of the phase change enthalpy and the phase change temperature, respectively. The lowest temperature was set at -30 °C or -20 °C and the highest temperature at 30 °C to guarantee that the entire samples volume was melted before the next cooling cycle. The experiments were conducted using hermetically sealed, $40\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ aluminium crucibles under a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 50 ml/min . Each sample underwent three heating and cooling cycles at 2 K/min and three heating and cooling cycles at 10 K/min. The melting (T_m) and crystallization (T_c) temperatures were calculated by the STARe software through the tangent method, and the enthalpies (ΔH) were obtained by integration of the corresponding peaks. The degree of subcooling, ΔT , was calculated using the difference between the onset melting temperature and the onset crystallization temperature reported by the instrument. T_m and T_c were determined using the cycles conducted at 2 K/min while ΔH was determined based on the cycles conducted at 10 K/min. The method used is based on the one developed in [15].

Determination of subcooling

As already mentioned, the subcooling of the material was measured in the DSC with a sample quantity of 5 - 20 mg. However, since a small sample quantity leads to an overestimated subcooling compared to the application, it was also measured using a 30 ml sample. For this purpose, the experimental setup for the cycling test was used, in which the temperatures were recorded. PT100 temperature sensors calibrated in ice water were used as the temperature sensors. For subcooling, the average of the first 10 measurements was taken. An example of a cooling cycle is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Example of subcooling of PCM SU11 in a 30 ml sample

Determination of density

The densities were determined at room temperature (24.5 °C) while all samples were in a liquid state. Initially 1 ml of the PCM was measured using a 1 ml GILSON pipette. The sample was subsequently placed in a Mettler Toledo weighing balance (Model MT5, series number L59982) where its mass was measured. The density was calculated by dividing the sample mass by the sample volume. The measurements were repeated four times. The values reported are the mean values obtained from the repetitions.

As the only exception, the PCM Rubitherm SP5 gel was measured with the Mettler Todelo dm 40. For this measurement, the instrument was first calibrated with deionised water according to the manufacturer's procedure, then three measurements were performed at 25.0 °C.

3.2.1.2 Results

Results of phase change temperature and phase change enthalpy

Table 7 summarizes the phase change temperatures and enthalpies as determined in the framework on this study and reported in literature. It is worth mentioning that only melting temperatures could be found in literature. In most cases, it was also not mentioned if they referred to onset or peak melting points. In this investigation, it was considered useful to report both onset temperatures for the melting and crystallisation processes as an indication of the ability of the PCM to undergo phase change in a relatively narrow temperature range. Subcooling is discussed in more detail in the part titled "Results of the subcooling measurement".

Table 7 Measured phase change temperatures and enthalpies of fusion

PCM	T _{m, onset} °C	T _{c, onset} °C	T _{m, lit.} °C	Δh _m kJ/kg	Δh _{m, lit.} kJ/kg	Δh _{m, vol.} kWh/m ³	C _{p, solid lit.} kJ/K kg	C _{p, liquid lit.} kJ/K kg	Source lit.
Rubitherm SP5 gel	3.9	-36.9	5	140	170	52.3	2.0	n.a.	data sheet
n-Tetradecane	6.0	2.6	6	216	230	46.2	2.21	1.68	[11]
TBAB / water (32/68)	9.8	-10.7	9.8	162	200	47.0	n.a.	n.a.	[14]
Sunamp SU11	8.1	-10.1	11	151	126	44.7	2.2	1.8	data sheet
Sunamp SU5	4.2	0.0	5.5	147	190	35.8	2.3	1.8	data sheet

Results of the subcooling measurements

Two PCMs did not show any indications on subcooling in the 30 ml setup. These are Rubitherm SP5 gel and n-tetradecane. Sunamp SU5 shows almost no subcooling with 0.15 K. For TBAB, subcooling of 8 °C was measured, and for SU11, subcooling of 10 °C was measured. The results can be seen in Table 8. For comparison, the respective subcooling of the DSC sample with a sample content of 5 -20 mg is given.

Table 8 Subcooling of the 30 ml sample and DSC measurement (5 - 20 mg)

	Rubitherm SP5 gel	n-Tetradecane	TBAB / water (32/68)	SU5	SU11
30 ml	0 K	0 K	7.86 K	0.15 K	10.0 K
DSC	40.8 K	3.35 K	20.5 K	4.1 K	18.2 K

Results of the density measurements

Table 9 presents the densities of the six PCMs as they were measured in the framework of this study and reported in literature. The experimental results show a very high accuracy and a very good agreement with the values presented in literature. Therefore, these values are considered reliable and are utilised for the calculation of the volumetric enthalpies of the PCM. Nevertheless, it must be noted that the value of potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate deviates at 9% relatively strongly from the literature value. However, since potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate was not used for the reasons already mentioned, this deviation was not further investigated. As expected, salt/water mixtures present higher densities than organic substances. The PCM n-tetradecane has the lowest density, followed by Sunamp SU5.

Table 9 Densities determined experimentally in present study (at 24.5 °C) and reported in literature

PCM	Density 1 [g/ml]	Density 2 [g/ml]	Density 3 [g/ml]	Density 4 [g/ml]	Density mean [g/ml]	Density sd [g/ml]	Density lit [g/ml]
Potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate	1.5453	1.5439	1.5429	1.5438	1.5440	0.0009	1.42 [12]
Rubitherm SP5 gel ²	1.3404	1.3462	1.3420	n.a.	1.3429	0.0030	1.35 (data sheet)
n-Tetradecane	0.77	0.7655	0.7723	0.7699	0.7694	0.0025	0.76 [11]
TBAB / water (32/68)	1.0561	1.0446	1.0308	1.0327	1.0411	0.0102	1.07 [14]
Sunamp SU11	1.0661	1.0587	1.0616	1.0699	1.0641	0.0043	1.06 (data sheet)
Sunamp SU5	0.8888	0.8647	0.8807	0.8787	0.8782	0.0087	0.870 (data sheet)

3.2.2 Cycle stability

The cycle stability test is intended to examine the PCM for its longevity over many thermal cycles. This test reveals possible trends such as separation and changes in enthalpy or melting point.

3.2.2.1 Material and method

Within this study, all PCM candidates were cycled 200 times, i.e., solidified and melted 200 times. In each case, three samples per PCM were cycled in 30 ml HDPE containers. The experimental setup was operated with a Huber Unistat 510 thermostat using Bluesil Fluid 47 V 10 thermal oil. The temperature profile used is shown in Figure 7. The oil temperature near the sample and one sample temperature per PCM were monitored with PT100 temperature sensors. These were calibrated with ice water at the beginning of the test.

Figure 7 Temperature profile of the cycling setup

To be able to make a statement about the stability, a DSC measurement was carried out at the beginning as well as after 200 cycles. The melting temperature (onset temperature) and the enthalpy were evaluated. The DSC measurement was carried out according to the method described in 3.2.1.1 under "Determination of phase change temperature and phase change enthalpy".

² Measured with the density meter Mettler Todelo dm 40 at 25.0 °C.

3.2.2.2 Results

The results from the DSC measurements are shown below. There is one graph per PCM for the enthalpy and one for the onset temperature, with the three samples shown in different colours. The bars of the data points represent the standard deviation of the scatter.

Rubitherm SP5 gel

Figure 8 Results cycle stability test Rubitherm SP5 gel: left enthalpy, right onset temperature

Rubitherm SP5 gel behaves stably according to the results from the DSC (Figure 8), despite a visual separation observed in the samples.

n-Tetradecane

Figure 9 Results cycle stability test n-tetradecane: left enthalpy, right onset temperature

The PCM n-tetradecane shows a slight increase in onset temperature of about 1 Kelvin. The enthalpy, despite showing a high scattering (187-215 J/g before cycling and 197-210 J/g after cycling), exhibits a rather stable behaviour before and after the 200 cycles. Figure 9 shows the results of the measurement.

TBAB

Figure 10 Results cycle stability test TBAB: left enthalpy, right onset temperature

The enthalpy of TBAB shows a high scattering, especially before cycling (142-182 J/g). However, no decrease in the average enthalpy was observed after cycling. Similarly, to n-tetradecane, an onset temperature increase of about 1 Kelvin is observed (Figure 10).

Sunamp SU5

Figure 11 Results cycle stability test SU5: left enthalpy, right onset temperature

Sunamp SU5 demonstrated very stable values before and after cycling and a slight increase in onset temperature of about 1 Kelvin. Figure 11 shows the results of the measurement.

Sunamp SU11

Figure 12 Results cycle stability test SU11: left enthalpy, right onset temperature

With about 2.5 K onset temperature increase, Sunamp SU11 shows a change in melting point after 200 cycles. However, the enthalpy remains constant (Figure 12).

Overall, all five candidates showed good cycling stability with small variations in performance after cycling and no apparent degradation in their evaluated properties.

3.2.3 Material compatibility

All PCM candidates were tested with respect to their compatibility with the typical materials they are in contact in a Sunamp Cold Battery. In particular, the PCMs were tested in combination with metallic heat exchanger materials (aluminium, copper, and their combination) and surrounding plastic and rubber samples (polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), neoprene and butyl rubber). It should be noted at this point that the corrosion test was carried out with potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate due to the great potential of the energy density and the relatively low price. The results are shown in this section.

3.2.3.1 Material and method

A limited amount of information can be found in literature regarding the compatibility of PCMs with various metals and plastics in general [16], [17], [18] and even less so for PCMs used in cooling applications in particular [19]. There is no standardised methodology for material compatibility tests in the latent storage community and most researchers develop their own testing procedure. In this study, it was decided to follow standards that have been developed and established by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM G31 and ASTM D543).

Metals

Figure 13 shows an example of the untreated metallic samples. To determine the corrosion rate of the different metals in contact with the chosen PCMs, immersion tests of the metallic samples in the PCMs were performed. For each PCM three tests were conducted: one with aluminium, one with copper and one with a combined aluminium/copper sample to account for galvanic effects.

Figure 13 Metal specimens for material compatibility tests: (1) aluminium (15 x 15 x 0.1 mm), (2) copper (ø 7 mm / 6.4 x 15 mm), (3) copper and aluminium

The calculation of the surface area was made using the volume or mass of the samples.

For the copper samples, the diameter was assumed to be exact and constant. Measurements were made with the TESA-CAL 150 mm digital calliper. The following relationship therefore applies. Here S stands for the surface area, m for the mass, D for the outer diameter and d for the inner diameter.

$$S_{Cu} = S_{ring} + S_{sheath} = \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot (D^2 - d^2) + \frac{4 \cdot m}{\rho \cdot (D - d)}$$

For the aluminium samples, the surfaces at the edges were neglected and the sheet thickness was assumed to be exact and constant. The sheet thickness was measured with the TESA ISOMASTER

0...25/0.01 micrometre, resulting in the following relationship (S stands for surface area, V for volume, t for thickness, m for mass, and ρ for density):

$$S_{Al} = 2 \cdot \frac{V}{t} = \frac{2 \cdot m}{\rho \cdot t}$$

All metallic samples were cleaned according to ISO 8407:2009 (about 2-5 min). Subsequently, they were weighed in a balance (Ohaus EP214C for copper and Mettler Toledo MT5 for aluminium) and they were placed in a 50 ml Falcon tube containing 18-22 ml PCM. The immersion test was carried out at 40 °C for 30 days. After the immersion tests were completed, the metallic samples were removed from the PCM. They were mechanically cleaned with a soft brush, to remove most of the corrosion product so that the weight of the remaining metal could be measured. . After drying, the weight of the samples was measured. Subsequently, the samples were subjected to chemical cleaning in order to remove any remaining corrosion product, based on the norm [20]. For the chemical cleaning, aluminium samples were placed in nitric acid 70 wt.% and the copper samples were placed in HCl 23 wt.%. The samples were left in their corresponding acid for 50 to 120 seconds in total and they were removed, dried and weighed at regular intervals of 10 (with low mass loss up to 40) seconds to distinguish between the removal of the corrosion product as opposed to pure metal, as explained in [20]. The average, area-specific corrosion rate was then calculated as follows:

$$\text{Corrosion Rate} = \frac{m_e - m_i}{S_i \cdot t}$$

Where m_e is the final sample mass after removing all corrosion product and t is the time of exposure of the metal to the PCM. S stands for the surface area.

However, the interpretation of the corrosion rate is very application specific. For this reason, an estimate of the service life was made from the corrosion rate. Some assumptions were made for this purpose. Among other things, the calculation applies only to a heat exchanger with copper tubes and aluminium fins. This means that aluminium will be in contact with PCM on both sides and copper on one side. Furthermore, the corrosion rate is assumed to be constant, which is a rather conservative assumption. From this, the time required for complete decomposition of each material is calculated. The calculation is as follows:

$$\text{time}_{Al} = \frac{\delta_{Al} \cdot \rho_{Al}}{2 \cdot r} \quad \text{time}_{Cu} = \frac{\delta_{Cu} \cdot \rho_{Cu}}{r}$$

Where δ is the wall thickness, ρ is the density, and r is the respective corrosion rate of the test.

Polymers

For their different Heat and Cold Batteries, Sunamp utilises polypropylene, linear medium density polyethylene or butyl rubber as the encapsulation material. For this compatibility study, samples of about 2.25 cm² were taken from each of the three types of plastic/rubber. The specimens were weighed with a balance (Ohaus EP214C) and their initial mass, m_i , was recorded. The sample was then placed into a 50 ml Falcon tube and filled up with 18-22 ml PCM. The guideline ASTM D543 recommend that "the quantity of reagent shall be approximately 40 ml/in² of specimen surface area [21]. Three replicates of each sample were made. They were stored at room temperature for one week, after which the samples were removed, rinsed with deionised water, dried, and immediately reweighed and the weight, m_e , was recorded. The samples were then left to dry at room temperature for an additional week and the mass, m_d , was recorded. Based on this, the mass loss or gain after drying was calculated as follows:

$$\Delta m(\%) = \frac{m_{e,d} - m_i}{m_i} \cdot 100\%$$

The mass change is positive or negative depending on whether the sample gained or lost weight during the experiments.

Figure 14 Plastic samples for material compatibility test: (1) polypropylene (15 x 15 x 6 mm); (2) polypropylene (15 x 15 x 4.5 mm); (3) butyl rubber (15 x 15 x 1.9 mm)

3.2.3.2 Results

Metals

The results of the measurements are shown in Table 10, where the surface area was calculated as in the subsection above. The starting weight is the mass of the cleaned sample before it is placed in the PCM. The final weight is the approximate mass according to the ISO 8407:2009 standard, from which the corrosion rate can be determined. The average of the three samples is shown graphically and numerically in Figure 15. High corrosion rates were measured for both the Rubitherm SP5 gel and TBAB / water (32/68). In the case of TBAB / water (32/68), galvanic corrosion is also evident in the combined sample. In addition, the aluminium is affected by pitting corrosion. No strong corrosivity could be detected in the other PCMs. The conversion of the corrosion rate into the number of operating years is shown in Figure 16.

Table 10 Measurement results of the metal samples for the material compatibility test

PCM	Metal, Test number	Surface [mm ²]	Weight start [mg]	Weight end [mg]	Corrosion rate [mg/(m ² .day)]
Potassium Fluoride tetra-/dihydrate (57/43)	Al 1	627.81	84.755	84.612	7.59
	Al 2	603.64	81.491	81.357	7.40
	Al 3	606.86	81.926	81.796	7.14
	Cu 1	619.18	815.2	815.1	5.38
	Cu 2	599.83	789.2	789	11.11
	Cu 3	620.74	817.3	817.2	5.37
	mix Al1	624.94	84.367	84.254	6.03
	mix Cu 1	591.28	777.7	777.7	0.00
	mix Al2	596.42	80.517	80.38	7.66
	mix Cu 2	617.09	812.4	812.4	0.00
	mix Al3	615.52	83.095	82.973	6.61
	mix Cu 3	602.73	793.1	793	5.53
Rubitherm	Al 1	581.21	78.464	75.525	168.56

	Al 2	601.84	81.249	78.483	153.20	
	Al 3	597.36	80.644	77.742	161.93	
	Cu 1	604.97	796.1	790.8	292.03	
	Cu 2	625.50	823.7	818.4	282.44	
	Cu 3	607.20	799.1	793.8	290.95	
	mix Al1	629.21	84.944	81.989	156.54	
	mix Cu 1	617.02	812.3	812.2	5.40	
	mix Al2	617.13	83.313	80.201	168.09	
	mix Cu 2	576.25	757.5	757	28.92	
	mix Al3	614.73	82.988	79.996	162.24	
	mix Cu 3	617.61	813.1	812.7	21.59	
n-tetradecane	Al 1	606.85	81.925	81.661	14.50	
	Al 2	620.28	83.738	83.47	14.40	
	Al 3	614.10	82.903	82.696	11.24	
	Cu 1	592.02	778.7	778.7	0.00	
	Cu 2	613.75	807.9	807.9	0.00	
	Cu 3	594.03	781.4	781.3	5.61	
	mix Al1	620.29	83.739	83.541	10.64	
	mix Cu 1	631.53	831.8	831.8	0.00	
	mix Al2	635.79	85.831	85.497	17.51	
	mix Cu 2	644.55	849.3	849.1	10.34	
	mix Al3	630.71	85.146	84.829	16.75	
mix Cu 3	578.92	761.1	760.9	11.52		
TBAB / water (32/68)	Al 1	607.49	82.011	81.478	29.25	
	Al 2	612.97	82.751	82.338	22.46	
	Al 3	578.53	78.102	77.72	22.01	
	Cu 1	613.67	807.8	799.5	450.84	
	Cu 2	625.50	823.7	815.7	426.32	
	Cu 3	610.03	802.9	793.3	524.57	
	mix Al1	604.85	81.655	76.714	272.30	
	mix Cu 1	618.95	814.9	814.2	37.70	
	mix Al2	635.24	85.757	82.041	194.99	
	mix Cu 2	579.82	762.3	761.8	28.74	
	mix Al3	595.89	80.445	76.107	242.66	
mix Cu 3	599.01	788.1	787.4	38.95		
SU1	1	Al 1	626.90	84.631	84.556	3.99

	Al 2	618.23	83.461	83.404	3.07
	Al 3	622.55	84.044	83.969	4.02
	Cu 1	608.02	800.2	799.5	38.38
	Cu 2	619.25	815.3	814.6	37.68
	Cu 3	624.31	822.1	820.8	69.41
	mix Al1	621.52	83.905	83.821	4.51
	mix Cu 1	604.22	795.1	793.9	66.20
	mix Al2	597.21	80.624	80.514	6.14
	mix Cu 2	616.57	811.7	810.8	48.66
	mix Al3	566.81	76.519	76.43	5.23
	mix Cu 3	621.41	818.2	817.4	42.91
SU5	Al 1	632.47	85.384	85.299	4.48
	Al 2	623.41	84.161	84.083	4.17
	Al 3	615.66	83.114	83.036	4.22
	Cu 1	602.14	792.3	791.8	27.68
	Cu 2	604.15	795.0	794.7	16.55
	Cu 3	606.68	798.4	798	21.98
	mix Al1	612.50	82.688	82.57	6.42
	mix Cu 1	618.73	814.6	814.4	10.77
	mix Al2	554.99	74.923	74.84	4.99
	mix Cu 2	625.35	823.5	823.5	0.00
	mix Al3	616.14	83.179	83.063	6.28
	mix Cu 3	581.08	764.0	763.9	5.74

Figure 15 Mean corrosion rate of the metal samples from the material compatibility test

Figure 16 Number of operating years for the aluminium-copper heat exchanger

It is worth mentioning that methodology utilised for the corrosion tests enabled the determination of only one average corrosion rate, which accounted for the events occurring during the entire immersion tests. However, the corrosion rate typically exhibits a transient behaviour, and presents a higher value during the first days of immersion, which is reduced over the days and reaches a steady, lower corrosion rate after some days/weeks. The authors chose to use this average corrosion rate as an indicator of the material compatibility as it represents the maximum possible value for this specific temperature level (25°C). This is therefore a conservative, worst-case scenario approach, which gives confidence that the materials determined as compatible will perform even better than expected.

Plastics

Figure 17 shows the mass gain of each plastic sample directly after its extraction, rinsing and drying (day 0 after conclusion of immersion test), which is directly correlated to the degree of uptake of the PCM by the polymer. Whereas small degrees of swelling can be acceptable, higher degrees can cause alteration of the thermomechanical properties of the polymer, pressure increase and leakage of the PCM through the polymeric enclosure. Figure 18 shows the sample mass gain/loss with respect to its initial mass after 7 days of drying. These results should indicate whether any swelling was reversible, and whether extraction of soluble constituents took place.

In general, the PCMs n-tetradecane and Sunamp SU5 cause the plastics to swell strongly. In addition, it can also be seen that butyl rubber swells the most for all PCMs, followed by polypropylene. When the results for the individual PCMs are examined in more detail, the very good compatibility of the plastics with potassium fluoride tetra-/dihydrate, Rubitherm SP5 gel and TBAB is striking. TBAB causes butyl rubber to swell by 2%. After 7 days of drying, the sample returned to its original weight, but it is not possible to say with certainty whether any additives were washed out. With Sunamp SU11, swelling of polypropylene and butyl rubber was observed. In the case of butyl rubber, there was also a loss of mass after 7 days of drying, indicating that additives were washed out. How much additives were washed out of polypropylene cannot be determined after 7 days. However, it is certain that polyethylene is compatible with Sunamp SU11.

Figure 17 Mass gain % 0 days after extraction from the liquid PCM and drying at room temperature.

Figure 18 Mass gain % 7 days after extraction from the liquid PCM and drying at room temperature.

3.3 Decision

Table 11 summarises the results of the research conducted in this project and attempts to evaluate the PCMs in terms of their suitability as a storage medium in refrigeration latent storage systems. All PCMs have weaker and stronger performance ranges and there is no ideal candidate. However, some candidates stand out and others must be excluded due to certain mandatory criteria.

Rubitherm SP5 gel has a high energy density but is corrosive to metals, especially aluminium. Therefore, Rubitherm SP5 gel does not meet a mandatory criterion. TBAB is also corrosive to aluminium, which therefore also violates a mandatory criterion. Sunamp SU5 as well as n-tetradecanes behave similarly with regards to swelling and extraction behaviour with plastics. The extent to which this can be problematic for the specific application is not dealt with in this study. Sunamp SU11 exhibits very good material compatibility and compared to the other candidates, the energy density of 45 kWh/m³ is in the midfield.

Table 11 Summary of PCM properties determined in the framework of this project. The cell colour indicated the suitability of each determined property for a latent storage application. Red: not suitable; light red: possibly not suitable; light green: suitable under restrictions; green: suitable with good performance; dark green: suitable with very good performance.

	Thermophysical properties			Corrosion rate [mg/(m ² d)]				Compatibility with polymers		
	Δh [kWh/m ³]	T_m [°C]	ΔT [°C] 30 ml	Al	Cu	Al mix	Cu mix	PE	PP	BR
Rubitherm SP5 gel	52	3.9	0	160	290	160	19	no swelling, no extraction	no swelling, no extraction	swelling, no extraction
n-Tetradecane	46	6.0	0	13	1.9	15	7.3	swelling, lim. Extraction	swelling, extraction	swelling, extraction
TBAB	47	9.8	7.86	25	470	204	35	no swelling, no extraction	no swelling, no extraction	swelling, no extraction
SU11	45	8.1	10.0	3.7	48	5.3	53	no swelling, no extraction	swelling, no extraction	swelling, lim. Extraction
SU5	36	4.2	0.15	4.3	22	5.9	5.5	swelling, lim. Extraction	swelling, extraction	swelling, extraction

The summary of all candidates with consideration of the weighting is shown in Figure 19. Sunamp SU11 is the best overall. Thus, Sunamp SU11 is recommended for further pursuit based on current knowledge. However, Sunamp SU5 as well as n-tetradecane are two possible alternatives. At this point, attention is again drawn to the two PCMs Parafol 14-97 and Rubitherm RT5, which are chemically identical to n-tetradecane. The candidates outlined in red do not meet a mandatory criterion.

Figure 19 Performance of all PCM candidates with weighting factors considered. On the axis, the rating 5 is the maximum, 0 is the minimum rating. All candidates framed in red do not fulfil at least one mandatory criterion. On the right is the legend for the assignment of the colours.

4 PCM vessels and integration into MiniStor system

4.1 PCM vessels

The containment vessels for both the hot and cold PCMs will use the same components as Sunamp's UniQ range of Heat Batteries. The heat exchanger is submerged in the PCM and encapsulated in a polypropylene case for the hot PCM and a polyethylene case for the cold PCM. The case is surrounded by insulation and finally an outer aluminium case (see Figure 20). Each model in the UniQ range has the same footprint but different heights.

Figure 20: Schematic of the Sunamp UniQ Heat Battery.

The heat exchanger consists of two separate but interleaved circuits with the high power circuit comprising 66% of the volume and the low power circuit comprising 33% of the volume. This allows two different heat transfer fluids to be used, e.g. a technical fluid can be used to charge the hot PCM via the low power circuit and water can be used to discharge the hot PCM, providing domestic hot water or space heating. A vertical string of 3 temperature sensors is placed in a sensor pocket running through the centre of the heat exchanger for control of charging.

4.2 Connection to MiniStor

The two heat batteries (for domestic hot water and space heating) are connected to the MiniStor system in such a way to allow charging of the heat batteries via several different sources:

- 1) the TCM reactor during its discharging phase;
- 2) the solar thermal panels, via the inertia tank;
- 3) the heat pump.

Which source is used depends on the availability of the source. When a heat battery needs to be charged, the PCM control system sends a signal ("call for heating") to the higher level MiniStor control system, which directs the flow of hot water through one of the heat exchanger circuits to charge (i.e. melt) the PCM. The minimum flow temperature required to charge the SU58 Heat Batteries is 63 °C, and the maximum flow rate ranges from 6-25 L/min depending on the size of the Battery. The Heat Battery is charged when the return temperature reaches a minimum of 62 °C. Then the "call for heating" signal is turned off by the PCM control system and the MiniStor control system stops the flow of hot water through the heat battery.

When there is a need for hot water or space heating, water flows through the second of the two circuits in the heat exchanger or the relevant heat battery, transferring the heat from the PCM to the water and into the property.

The cold battery, for space cooling, is connected to the evaporator of the TCM system. The cold battery is charged (i.e. frozen) during the discharging phase of the TCM. If the cold battery needs to be charged, the PCM control system sends a signal ("call for cooling") to the higher level MiniStor control system, which directs the flow of cold water (around 0 °C) from the evaporator through one of the heat exchanger circuits of the cold battery. The maximum flow temperature required to charge the SU11 Cold Battery is 8 °C and the maximum flow rate ranges from 6-25 L/min depending on the size of the Battery. The Cold Battery is charged when the return temperature reaches a maximum of 9 °C. Then the "call for cooling" signal is turned off by the PCM control system and the MiniStor control system diverts the flow of cold water from the cold battery to a fan coil.

Conclusions

Sunamp's SU58 PCM was chosen for the hot PCM as it fulfils the high-power and energy density requirements for providing hot water and has been commercially available as part of Sunamp's Heat Batteries for several years. Sunamp's UniQ range of thermal stores is the first in the world to be awarded A grade RAL certification, with the lifetime of the PCM being >25 years.

In this study, five of eleven PCMs from literature research were tested for their suitability for refrigeration applications. The focus was placed on obtaining comparable data for all important thermophysical properties of the PCMs to enable a fair comparison. Additionally, immersion tests were conducted to determine the compatibility of the PCM with commonly used metals and polymers. In addition, cycle tests were conducted to assess the longevity of the five PCM candidates. For this study, 200 cycles were performed.

Of course, for a given application, the melting point is also an important criterion for PCM selection. While the measured densities were consistent with the ones reported in literature, some significant deviations were observed when comparing the melting points and enthalpies of fusion. This highlights the importance of using consistent methodologies to determine thermophysical properties when the goal is to compare PCM performance.

According to the measurement results, Sunamp SU11 is the best option for the desired application. The very good material compatibility with the tested plastics PP, PE and BR as well as the tested metals copper and aluminium is convincing. The energy density of 45 kWh/m³, however, is not outstanding, but within the range of the tested candidates. With Sunamp SU5 and n-tetradecane there are interesting alternatives with a phase change temperature of 5 °C.

The containment vessels for both the hot and cold PCMs will use the same components as Sunamp's UniQ product range. The heat exchangers will be immersed in the PCM and encapsulated in a polypropylene case (for the hot PCM) or a polyethylene case (for the cold PCM). The cases are surrounded by insulation and placed into an outer aluminium case.

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